

Accurately Locate Smartphones Using Seeker

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Abstract—:In this digitally-driven world, Geo location tracking is a crucial technology required for tracking gadgets or humans. Seeker utilizes HTML5, JavaScript, JQuery and PHP to grab Device Information and Geo-Location with High Accuracy. Seeker Tool Hosts a fake website on Apache Server and employment Ngrok to create an SSL link. It asks for Location Permission. If the user permits it, we will get Longitude, Latitude, Accuracy Direction, Altitude and Speed. Without any permissions, we get device information such as Operating System, Platform, Number of CPU Cores, Amount of RAM, GPU information, Browser Name, Screen Resolution, Version and Public IP Address.

Keywords— Seeker, Geo location, SET, Ngrok

I. INTRODUCTION

Kali Linux is enterprise-ready security reviewing Linux conveyance based on Debian GNU/Linux. Kali is pointed at security experts and IT administrators, empowering them to conduct progressed penetration testing, legal examination, and security reviewing. Kali Linux was born and released on March 13th, 2013. It's a security-focused adaptation of Linux that provides expansive number of tools to look for out shortcomings and secure your network. Kali contains several tools which are equipped towards different data security assignments, such as Penetration Testing, Security inquire about, Computer Forensics and Invert Designing. It was created by Mati Aharoni and Devon Kearns of Offensive Security through the rewrite of Backtrack, their past data security testing Linux dispersion. Kali Linux is the world's most effective and well known penetration testing stage, utilized by security. [1][2]

A. Features and other information of Kali Linux includes:

- More than 600 penetration testing tools in kali
- OS Family - Unix like
- Working State - Active
- Platforms - x86, x86-64, armhf, armel
- Kernel Type - Monolithic kernel (Linux)
- Default UI - GNOME3
- Latest Release – 2018.1 Feb 6, 2018
- Wide-ranging wireless device support

B. History of Kali Linux

- Knoppix, ancestor of Kali Linux was the first ever

bootable live Linux Operating System, Which is still in existence. [1]

- Knoppix project was then forked into Whoppix and after that re-forked into WHAX.[1]
- WHAX was at that point re-branded and streamlined into the BackTrack, the forerunner of Kali Linux.
- BackTrack had a long rule of nearly seven years as the write analyzers and hacker's choice. [1]
- BackTrack may be a customized local environment committed to hacking. As of 2011 it was utilized by more than four million novice and proficient security researchers. [1]

C. Penetration Testing

Penetration testing (too called pen testing) is the hone of testing a Web application or computer system, network to discover vulnerabilities that an assailant could exploit. For case, a review or an appraisal may utilize scanning tools that give a few hundred conceivable vulnerabilities on different systems. A Penetration Test would attempt to assault those vulnerabilities within the same way as a malicious hacker to verify which vulnerabilities are veritably reducing the genuine list of system vulnerabilities to a modest bunch of security weaknesses.[1][2]

Different Strategies

- Targeted testing
- External testing
- Internal testing
- Blind testing

D. Benefits of Penetration Testing

- Intelligently control vulnerabilities
- avoid the value of network downtime
- Meet regulatory necessities and avoid fines
- keep company image and consumer loyalty

II. SEEKER

Seeker is a tool which is used to accurately locate smartphones using social engineering. With the help of this Seeker we can trace live location of victims using kali Linux.

Like other phishing pages to get the users credentials we host a fake page that requests users location like many popular location based websites. Seeker Hosts a fake webpage which asks for Location Permission and if the Victim allows we can get their location and without permission we device details. It also provides the Google maps link.

Seeker makes use of HTML API and gets location Permission and then grabs Longitude and latitude utilizing GPS hardware which is present in the device, so Seeker works pleasant with Smartphones, if the GPS hardware isn't always present, together with on a laptop, Seeker fallbacks to IP Geolocation or it'll seek for Cached Coordinates. Usually if a user permits location access, Accuracy of the data received is accurate to approximately 30 meters.

The Available templates are Near You, Google Drive, WhatsApp and Telegram.

Accuracy relies upon on a couple of elements which you can or may not manage along with:

- Device - may not work on laptops or mobile that have damaged GPS.
- Browser - a few browsers block JavaScript.
- GPS Calibration - If GPS isn't calibrated you may get erroneous outcomes and that is very not unusual.

A. Features

- Geo Location: With the help of Seeker tool we can trace anyone's Geo location. It provides location details such as :
 - Longitude
 - Latitude
 - Accuracy
 - Altitude – Not always available
 - Direction
 - Speed
 - Google Map link
- Device Information: Seeker Provides device information of victims such as :
 - Operating System
 - Platform
 - Number of CPU Cores
 - Amount of RAM – Approximate Results
 - Screen Resolution
 - GPU information
 - Browser Name and Version
 - Public IP Address
- Other Location Information: It Provides other location information such as :
 - Continent

- Country
- Region
- City

B. Other Tools Which Is Used For This Purpose

The others tools which can be used for tracking location are `trape` and `trackUrl`.

TrackUrl

TrackUrl is similar to seeker tool, it is an effective tool that could track a person's actual location, and this tool run on Kali Linux is a bash/JS script for tracking places. TrackUrl is a tool to be able to create a URL when your victim visit that URL then it will ask your victim to permit region. While the victim lets in the place you gets the exact latitude and longitude of the victim.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

After Nikola Pavkovic, Luka Perkov et al. [3] in Social Engineering Toolkit – a scientific technique to Social Engineering, here it offers Social Engineering techniques, exploiting people as statistics structures security weakest hyperlink, vicinity unit basically the initial attack vectors at durations larger intrusions and expertise machine compromises. Social Engineering Toolkit (SET) is an incorporated set of tools designed mainly to carry out superior attacks against the human part and is that the most advanced, if now not the sole toolkit of such type that's publically reachable as open-supply computer code. This paper presents a short introduction to the Social Engineering Toolkit computer code design and offers a summary of supported attack vectors.

A more superior technique of filtering was used in [5]. In this paper, the authors tested the URLs and confirmed whether or not it was malicious or not. They used an automated technique for detecting phishing. It had phases Pre-filtering and category segment. Within the pre-filtering phase, the URL became in comparison towards a black list the usage of the domain a part of the URL. If the URL become present in that list then it was classified as malicious and might no longer be intending to the category phase. In the subsequent phase, two most important features have been checked for consistency-Randomness of the URL (RU) and the location of the domain token. Based totally on the effects of category phase, the URL was categorized as malicious or non-malicious.

Ahmed Mohammad Al-tarawneh & Alaa H Al-Hamami et al. [4] in Social Engineering attack the use of SET Toolkit packages in Kali Linux – IP deal with method, depicts social engineering attacks, with an partner experiment on Kali Linux software exploitation the Set package deal from the SET Toolkit, Social Engineering is that the artwork of manipulating people and build them to administer up counseling. SET may be a social engineering tool that inside the foremost concentrates at the offensive the human a part of safety. Social Engineering Toolkit package deal to enforce one in every of the social engineering attacks on Gmail accounts. Here it discusses the ways (attacks) of the Social Engineering on the social media structures as (Facebook, twitter and malicious software) like electronic mail, passwords or some private statistics throw social media systems.

IV. SOCIAL ENGINEERING

Social Engineering is collecting individual’s secret data. The frauds may get to diverse sorts of data, but when people are focused on the offenders may get to your passwords or bank data, or get to your computer to subtly introduce noxious software—that will grant them get to your passwords and bank data and giving them control of your computer. The aim of a social engineering attack is to keep away from cyber safety systems through, exploiting the weakest hyperlink, the human beings concerned. .at some point of the interplay, victims are unaware of the unfavorable nature of their actions. The social engineer exploits harmless instincts, not crook. Explicit techniques consisting of threats or bribery do not fall in the scope of social engineering. A skilled practitioner of this subject is familiar with and perceives social interaction patterns to manipulate the psychological elements of the human thoughts. With this decision, the attacker is successful of executing an efficient and reasonably-priced security compromise, without the want to make investments in breaking technical security features. Though, an educated social engineer on pc science may additionally also complement technological manner to the assault in order to perform the malicious intentions. [6][7]

A. Phishing

Phishing is one of the foremost well-known social engineering attack, phishing scams are text and email message campaigns. In most cases it host fake websites and all, it at that point nudges them into uncovering delicate data, clicking on joins to noxious websites, or opening records that contain malware. Normally, the targets are not able to distinguish among actual and phishing websites inflicting them to fall into the traps set via the phisher.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

Step-1: Clone this tool from its Github repository using following command:

git clone <https://github.com/thewhite4t/seeker>

Step-2: we need to run the installer.sh

So, the command will be: Sudo bash install.sh

Step-3: we manually start the tool on our localhost and forward our localhost to another ssh port forwarding service.

To run seeker we use following command:

Sudo ./seeker.py -t manual

Fig.1 .Seeker Home

Step-4: Now we can select the Template

0-Nearyou has been selected

Fig.2 .Seeker selecting template

Step-5: Now we need to start Ngrok server

Open a new Window

Now we need to connect your Ngrok account

Command-./ngrok authtoken code(from your Ngrok account)

Step-6: Now start server using the following code

./Ngrok http 8080

And we have started the server and here is the link we have to send to the victim, send the link to victim

Fig.3 .New window for Ngrok server

Step-7: Once the victim Open the link and give permission we will get the victims location details and Device details.

Fig.4 . Near You Home page

- Here is the Victims Location information and Device Information

```
OS : Android 10
Platform : Linux arm64
CPU Cores : 8
RAM : 4
GPU Vendor : Qualcomm
GPU : Adreno (TM) 618
Resolution : 393x873
Browser : Chrome/86.0.4340.198
Public IP : 2401:4900:3201:c5c1:f0b5:ca5a2:7690:d166
Continent : Asia
Country : India
Region : Uttar Pradesh
City : Noida
Org : None
ISP : None

Location Information :
Latitude : 16.1628456 deg
Longitude : 75.6772273 deg
Accuracy : 21.92200885009766 m
Altitude : 456.63629151998425
Direction : 227 deg
Speed : 1.570000024528874 m/s

Google Maps : https://www.google.com/maps/place/16.1628456,75.6772273
New Entry Added in Database : /home/ben/seeker/seeker/db/results.csv
Waiting for User Interaction...
```

Fig.5. Victims device and location details

Step-8: Now Copy the Google map link and open in browser

Fig.6. Victims Location

Known Problems of Seeker are Serveo and Ngrok are banned in some nations such as Russia etc., so if it's banned in your country you can no longer get a URL.

VI. NGROK

Ngrok is a multiplatform tunneling, reverse proxy software that establishes secure tunnels from a public endpoint such as net to a locally running network service while capturing all site visitors for designated inspection and replay. Which means that no domain name or public IP on the local system is needed. Ngrok creates both HTTPS and HTTP endpoints, making it useful for testing integrations with third-party offerings or APIs that require legitimate SSL/TLS domain names. In case you do not specify it, your net browser will connect to the default webservice port, that's port 80. Port eighty is the port range assigned to typically used net communication protocol, http.

VII. FUTURE WORK

Seeker gives the information about the device and it's Geo Location. Future work with this tool is it can be used for marketing purpose. Gadget shops can use this tool for personalized marketing, with help of seeker they can host a

fake web page which ask for location access or they can request location access from their own online shopping page. They can post the link of this fake web page in their social media pages, using extra social engineering they can shorten the link. Once customers give location access they will get their location and device details. Using the device details they can analyze the device used by the Customers and its specification. If the Customers are using old mobile/Laptop or device with low specifications we can recommend them updating their device or if they are using new device/device with good specification we can recommend them accessories for those device. We have got victims location also so we can send these product recommendations to victims as product catalogues and brochures.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Seeker is Geo Location identifier tool in Kali Linux, this offer specific location and device details of victim. There are other tool like trackUrl and Trape which can be used for location tracking but Seeker provide more accurate location and it also provide the device information. It use social engineering techniques to track the location. . The basic idea behind the tool is phishing. Using Phishing it host a fake web page on In Built PHP Server and uses Ngrok and request for location access and if the victim give permission we will get his location and device information. Using extra social engineering we can shorten the URL. If the victim doesn't allow the location access we will not get the location, we will only get the device details. Along with the Location details it will provide Google map link also so we can easily track the victim. Using Victims Device information we are able to analyze his device and its specifications. It provides accurate location and exact device information. It shows how a malicious website gather our information and why we shouldn't click on such kind of untrusted links.

REFERENCES

- [1] Georgia Weidman "Penetration Testing A Hands-On Introduction to Hacking.", pp. [87-112], June 2014.
- [2] Raphaël Hertzog, Jim O'Gorman, and Mati Aharoni "Kali Linux. Revealed. Mastering the Penetration Testing", pp. [1- 300] June 2017.
- [3] Nikola Pavković, Luka Perkov: Social Engineering Toolkit – A systematic approach to social engineering.
- [4] [2] Ahmed Mohamm Al-tarawneh & Alaa H Al-Hamami: Social Engineering attack using setoolkit packages in Kali Linux – IP address approach.
- [5] Yi-Shin Chen, Huei-Sin Liu, Yi-Hsuan Yu and Pang-Chieh Wang, Detect Phishing by Checking Content Consistency, IEEE, 2017.
- [6] "Hacking the human operating system: The role of social engineering within cybersecurity", Technical report, Intel Security, 2015.

Seppo Heikkinen, "Social engineering in the world of emerging communication technologies", Proceedings of Wireless World Research Forum, pp. 1-10, 2006.